

Deliverable D2.2 – COOPERATE Playbook - Release II

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Executive Summary

In the current geopolitical landscape with strong global competition and a pressing need for European independence, the translation of Europe's excellent research into real-life solution is more important than ever. The present COOPERATE Playbook (D2.2 COOPERATE Playbook – release II) is intended as a practical guide to enhancing knowledge valorisation in regional research and innovation (R&I) ecosystems by guiding their transition towards greater maturity. The Playbook revolves around seven lines of action which were identified by the COOPERATE consortium as being central pillars of a strong knowledge creation and valorisation ecosystem. The seven lines of action are Research, Talent, Knowledge transfer, Funding, Collaboration, Governance, and Innovation.

The COOPERATE Playbook highlights the indicators of strength along each line of action, detailing the hallmarks that describe an ideal, advanced level of maturity within regional knowledge ecosystems. Designed for ecosystem actors across the quadruple helix, meaning both universities and research organisations, the industry, public administration and policymakers, and NGOs representing the civil society, the COOPERATE Playbook describes the factors that are typically present in advanced ecosystems, contributing to their success.

In addition, the COOPERATE Playbook offers a Roadmap to guide emerging regional ecosystems towards greater maturity in their process of becoming an ERA Hub. This roadmap offers a step-by-step guide for ecosystems to engage the relevant stakeholders and begin the journey towards becoming an ERA Hub. The roadmap introduces the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool that can help regional ecosystems gauge their existing levels of maturity and the COOPERATE Toolbox containing 33 tried-and-true tools consolidating the consortium's collective expertise and leveraging best practice models that ecosystems can implement to improve their level of maturity. Finally, the roadmap introduces the COOPERATE Platform through which aspiring and existing ERA Hubs can connect, collaborate and access resources to support their development.

The COOPERATE Playbook was prepared by the Technical University of Denmark. The COOPERATE Playbook, Self-Assessment Digital Tool, Toolbox and Platform have all been co-developed with and validated by key stakeholders through a series of co-creation sessions (see D1.2 Report on Co-creation with CDTF and D1.3 Report on Co-creation with extended CDTF).

The present COOPERATE Playbook release II is a revised version of the COOPERATE Playbook release I. The most significant changes from release I to release II are as follows:

- The hallmarks describing each line of action have been revised to ensure alignment with the revised ERA Hub definition and the goal of increased knowledge valorisation.
- The “Recommendations for development” sections have been removed, as their purpose did not differ significantly from the much more concrete and actionable tools in the COOPERATE Toolbox. The main points from the Recommendations for development have been integrated in the tools. To create a clear link between the hallmarks and the tools, each hallmark has been supplemented by a list of supporting tools that an ecosystem can employ to advance in that specific respect.

- Unlike the COOPERATE Playbook release I, the COOPERATE Playbook release II contains a Roadmap, intended as a step-by-step guide to support an ecosystem's transition towards greater maturity. This includes brief introductions to the other tools developed as part of the COOPERATE project and how they are useful for the ecosystem on this journey.

List of abbreviations

ACRONYM	STANDS FOR
D	Deliverable
DX.X	Deliverable Number
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
R&I	Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

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Introduction

The European Union (EU) boasts a wealth of world-class research but lags behind its global competitors when it comes to translating this knowledge into practical solutions that benefit the wider society. In today's rapidly evolving geopolitical landscape, Europe's ability to withstand global pressure and competition has become a top priority. The present COOPERATE Playbook (hereinafter: the PLAYBOOK) is intended as a practical guide to assist ecosystems – European Research Area (ERA) Hubs - through their transition towards greater maturity. An ERA Hub is an ecosystem dedicated to improving knowledge valorisation, specifically defined in the COOPERATE project as follows:

*“An ERA Hub is an **ecosystem of quadruple helix actors** led by **universities** aiming at improving **knowledge valorisation** within their **region**.”*

The ERA Hub concept is described in greater detail in the ERA Hub Framework (D1.4 Final ERA Hub Framework model and KPIs).

The PLAYBOOK is designed for ecosystem actors across the quadruple helix, including academia, industry, public administration and the civil society. The PLAYBOOK describes the hallmarks of excellence along seven **lines of action**: Research, Talent, Knowledge transfer, Funding, Collaboration, Governance, and Innovation.

In addition, the PLAYBOOK offers a **Roadmap** to guide ERA Hubs towards greater maturity. This roadmap introduces the **COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool** (hereinafter: the SELF-ASSESSMENT) that can help ecosystems gauge their existing levels of maturity, and the **COOPERATE Toolbox** (hereinafter: the TOOLBOX) containing 33 concrete tools that the ecosystem can implement to improve their level of maturity. Finally, the roadmap introduces the **COOPERATE Platform** (hereinafter: the PLATFORM) through which aspiring and existing ERA Hubs can connect and access resources (including the COOPERATE tools) to support their development. The PLATFORM will also contain the present PLAYBOOK in a practitioner's version, attached here as Appendix A. The content of the practitioner's version is exactly the same but in a more compelling layout.

The PLAYBOOK was developed by the Technical University of Denmark based on observable traits of advanced regional R&I ecosystems. Both the PLAYBOOK, SELF-ASSESSMENT, TOOLBOX and PLATFORM have been co-developed with and validated by key stakeholders through a series of co-creation sessions (for further information see D1.2 Report on Co-creation with CDTF and D1.3 Report on Co-creation with extended CDTF).

Lines of action

This chapter details each of the seven lines of action, including the hallmarks of excellence that describe an ideal, advanced level of maturity. This model shows the seven lenses through which maturity is viewed in the ERA Hub framework and make up the foundation of the SELF-ASSESSMENT (D3.2 Digital tools in the project website) and the TOOLBOX (D2.4 COOPERATE Toolbox release II).

Figure 1 Illustration of the seven lines of action defined in the cooperate project: Research, Talent, Knowledge transfer, Funding, Collaboration, Governance and Innovation

The **Research** line of action is concerned with the contextual conditions that are required to ensure a sufficiently level of high-quality research outputs. It relates to the creation of an environment that enables scientific exploration, promoting interdisciplinarity and collaboration and strengthening research infrastructure. The production of high-quality knowledge is a fundamental prerequisite for knowledge valorisation.

Talent focuses on the critical aspect of developing, attracting and retaining top-tier research and innovation professionals, including the implementation of strategies for fostering talent development, promoting diversity and inclusion and establishing attractive career paths and living conditions. Highly skilled professionals are essential drivers of the production and valorisation of knowledge.

Knowledge transfer is a central element of knowledge valorisation and pertains to the creation of trusting relationships between ecosystem players, establishing solid knowledge transfer infrastructure and actively supporting knowledge transfer and dissemination through engaging activities. Sound mechanisms for knowledge transfer facilitate knowledge valorisation by ensuring that the knowledge

is accessed by the institutions and people capable of translating them into real-life solutions benefiting society.

Through the **Funding** line of action, the ecosystem must ensure that the available funding is sufficient to support both research and innovation in the ecosystem as well as ensuring the visibility and accessibility of funds and ensuring fairness and trust through transparent and merit-based grant practices. The availability of funding is fundamental to all initiatives within knowledge production and valorisation.

Collaboration is a cornerstone of successful ecosystem development, revolving around trust, openness to collaboration both internally in the ecosystem and internationally. It highlights the importance of shared goals and visions to drive tangible outcomes. Interconnectedness is a core element of knowledge valorisation as it allows the ecosystem to combine expertise and resources.

Governance structures ensure the sustainability and long-term success of ecosystem initiatives by promoting transparency, accountability, and fostering trust among stakeholders. This line of action addresses the need for legitimacy among decision-makers to ensure continued support for the activities of the ecosystem. Sound governance enables the establishment and implementation of joint goals within knowledge valorisation.

The **Innovation** line of action emphasises the need for a dynamic patent landscape, a nurturing environment for entrepreneurs, innovation infrastructure and intermediaries and a regulatory environment that support knowledge valorisation through innovation. Innovation and entrepreneurship are perhaps the most tangible forms of knowledge valorisation, directly translating the science and technology of the ecosystem into real-life solutions to society's problems.

In the sections below, each line of action is described in more detail, including the hallmarks of excellence that are indicative of advanced maturity. Each hallmark is supported by a number of tools that the ERA Hub can employ to advance their maturity in that particular respect. The tools are described in the TOOLBOX (D2.4 COOPERATE Toolbox release II).

1.1 Research

Research makes up the foundation of both the broader ERA initiative and the ERA Hub concept, specifically. The production of world-class research drives the development of solutions to societal problems, generating workplaces and economic growth while strengthening the ecosystem's reputation and ability to attract talent.

For the research ecosystem to ensure the sustained support of the wider public, it is necessary to promote transparency, accountability, and public engagement in the research process. This can be achieved through inviting open dialogue and communicating the societal relevance of research.

The hallmarks of a prosperous research ecosystem include:

- **Presence of large research and technology institutions**

Universities and research centres are the primary drivers of research and serve as focal points for advanced research and technology development. These institutions bring together experts and state-of-the-art facilities, providing a nurturing environment for interdisciplinary collaboration and the pursuit of transformative breakthroughs. The presence of multiple large research and technology institutions enhances the overall research output and contributes to the ecosystem's reputation.

Supporting tools: Centres of excellence, Industry sponsorships

- **Link to research infrastructure**

Producing world-class science requires access to world-class research infrastructure, such as laboratories, scientific instrumentation and technologies, data resources, and computational tools. An advanced ecosystem is characterised by investment in research infrastructure and equipment to increase the research capacity of the ecosystem. This equipment can be present in the ecosystem itself or, in the case of particularly complex, specialised, or expensive infrastructure, it can be accessed through collaborations with other ecosystems or scientific institutions (e.g. the Large Hadron Collider at CERN).

Supporting tools: Strategic partnerships, Industry sponsorships

- **Diversity of research areas**

The exploration of a diverse range of research areas supports interdisciplinary collaboration and fosters cross-pollination across science, engineering, and technology. This interdisciplinarity, particularly when further combined with social sciences and humanities, enables the ecosystem to creatively address a broad spectrum of research areas and develop comprehensive solutions to complex problems. This broad research capacity is generally reflected in the presence of a high number of faculties, institutes and research groups and contributes to the ecosystem's richness and relevance.

Supporting tools: Joint research initiatives, Industrial PhD

- **Continuous publication of high-quality science**

The consistent publication of high-quality science with high impact strengthens the ecosystem's influence and recognition within the scientific community. Research excellence is supported in an environment that enables research over longer time horizons and with sustained funding, as these extended projects allow for the thorough investigation that enables breakthrough discoveries.

Successful research ecosystems will place the strongest emphasis on research ethics and integrity to ensure the credibility and trustworthiness of research outcomes and ensure this through policies and guidelines that promote responsible conduct of research, data integrity, and transparent reporting.

Supporting tools: Commissioned research for industry, Commissioned research/analysis for government

1.2 Talent

Talent plays a central role in driving progress and ensuring adaptability in the ever-changing landscape of research and innovation. A diverse and well-developed talent pool will ensure robustness of the ecosystem and propel the creation and valorisation of knowledge, ultimately leading to sustainable progress and societal impact.

Nurturing talent through education is a cornerstone of ensuring the research and innovation capabilities required for the ecosystem to grow and develop a reputation for excellence. Through life-long education, both students and professionals are equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills to thrive in the research and innovation landscape.

In addition to developing home-grown talent, attracting and retaining talented individuals from outside the ecosystem is key. In order to be attractive to international top talent, the ecosystem must offer access to impactful research projects, state-of-the-art facilities, and funding opportunities in addition to attractive living conditions. Attracting diverse talent from different demographics and backgrounds is expected to foster greater creativity and innovation.

The hallmarks of strong talent development and retention in the ecosystem include:

- **Ability to develop talent**

An advanced talent ecosystem will emphasise education in order to develop a rich talent pool and a culture of learning, facilitating collaboration, knowledge exchange, and cross-pollination of ideas. The central node of the education landscape is the university, providing students and professionals with the skills and knowledge to excel in their respective fields through high-quality study programmes and life-long learning opportunities. These educational programmes are often co-developed with the local industry and designed to meet the demands of the employers to ensure both availability of talent and a high level of employment.

However, the educational institutions in the ecosystem should support the entirety of an individual's career. This spans early education, where early initiatives encourage children and young students from underrepresented backgrounds to pursue careers within research and innovation, degree programmes that are aligned with the needs of the ecosystem, and offering opportunities for continuous learning throughout the career.

In addition to formal education, mentorship programmes are powerful mechanisms to ensure both effective knowledge transfer and continuous development of the talent body. Mentorship networks connect experienced professionals with emerging researchers and innovators, providing guidance, support, and connections to accelerate the individual's learning and growth and increase the research and innovation capacity of the ecosystem as a whole.

Supporting tools: Career fair, Diversity outreach, Industry involvement in university courses, Mentorship programme

- **Ability to attract talent from outside the ecosystem**

The ability to attract talent from outside the boundaries of the ecosystem – both students and employees – demonstrates a reputation for excellence and a dedication to making the ecosystem an attractive destination for top talent. This interregional and international interest is typically a result of high-quality educational programmes, attractive workplaces with impactful research and funding opportunities, and an inclusive and welcoming living environment. The ecosystem should provide support to help international talent find affordable housing and childcare, integrate into the local community, and navigate cultural differences to help them and their families settle into the ecosystem.

The presence of talent coming from different cultural backgrounds fosters innovation and knowledge exchange and forges connections with other ecosystems, which in turn is expected to attract further talent from outside the ecosystem.

Supporting tools: Attractive living conditions, Exchange programmes

- **Ability to retain local and international talent**

The retention of top talent in the ecosystem is as important as developing and attracting this talent in the first place. This requires both attractive opportunities for career development, a culture that recognises and rewards excellence, and a high quality of life in the ecosystem, enabling the long-term engagement of expert professionals who contribute to the growth and success of the ecosystem.

Supporting tools: Industry-sponsored prizes, Targeted funding programmes for young talent

- **Critical mass of scientific personnel**

The presence of a significant number of skilled researchers, innovators and entrepreneurs within the ecosystem is a marker of a critical mass of talent in the ecosystem. A high concentration of talent enables the ecosystem to produce world-class work and further attract and retain top talent, thereby strengthening the research capacity for the ecosystem.

Supporting tools: Attractive living conditions

- **Dynamic job market with opportunities for career development across quadruple helix**

The opportunities for employees to develop their career and achieve international recognition is key to attracting top talent. A large number of companies and research institutions paired with a low level of unemployment for scientific personnel are indicators of a career landscape that allows researchers and innovators can find fulfilling career prospects.

Opportunities for continued education and training, participation in joint projects and the mobility of employees between employers across the quadruple helix strengthen the basis for collaboration, knowledge transfer and the development of best practices between ecosystem players.

Supporting tools: Exchange programmes, Joint research activities

1.3 Knowledge transfer

Knowledge transfer is at the heart of a strong research and innovation ecosystem. Sound technology transfer mechanisms ensure that scientific developments are applied in real-world contexts and accelerates societal development. Ensuring this flow of knowledge, expertise, and technology can lead to the development of new industries, job creation, and economic growth.

In addition to the application of technologies in real-life settings, knowledge transfer to the public ensures that research outcomes are accessible to a wider audience. Collaboration and dialogue with the public not only democratises knowledge but also helps build trust within the general population by showcasing relatable societal progress brought about by research and innovation.

One of the subtle yet powerful conductors of knowledge transfer are university students. As the students acquire knowledge, they also have the potential to disseminate it effectively into society. This can be through informal settings among family and friends or through their dispersion into the workforce after completing their studies. By fostering an inclusive and engaging learning environment, the students become integral to the research and innovation ecosystem, actively bridging the gap between academia and society.

The hallmarks of efficient knowledge transfer in the ecosystem include:

- **Well-established relationships between ecosystem players**

Advanced regional knowledge and innovation ecosystems often enjoy a high level of trust, transparency, integrity, and accountability, resulting in strong partnerships between academia, industry, government, and non-profit organisations.

Trusting relationships between ecosystem players are key to ensuring efficient knowledge sharing. Trust is fundamental for open knowledge sharing as it enables ecosystem members to share ideas without fearing that it will harm their business. Additionally, trust gives stakeholders confidence in the credibility and reliability of the knowledge being transferred.

Besides trust, transparency around who to talk to in the ecosystem, relationship anchor points in the organisations and openness to welcome new members into the ecosystem are indicators of healthy knowledge transfer relationships in an ecosystem.

Supporting tools: Central interest organisation, Stakeholder engagement forum, Stakeholder engagement platform

- **Effective knowledge transfer infrastructure internally in ecosystem and outside ecosystem**

An ecosystem with efficient knowledge transfer will have mechanisms such as such as joint research projects and industry-academic partnerships to ensure knowledge transfer both among the ecosystem players and between the ecosystem and the outside world. In addition, the mobility of students and employees through joint research initiatives and exchange programmes promote talent exchange and cross-cultural learning, and partnerships with researchers and organisations from around the world facilitate knowledge transfer, collaboration, and the sharing of best practices.

Open science practices, including open access publishing, sharing of research data, and collaboration on open-source projects maximise the visibility and impact of the research from the ecosystem. A culture of transparency, reproducibility, and sharing within the ecosystem facilitates collaboration, and accelerates the pace of scientific progress.

Supporting tools: Exchange programmes, Joint research projects, Tech transfer office

- **Engaging knowledge transfer activities**

Knowledge sharing and knowledge transfer can be facilitated through events and activities that engage different players in the ecosystem, including the general public. Engaging knowledge sharing and dissemination formats are essential in order to capture the attention and interest of stakeholders. Traditional modes of dissemination, such as academic papers, conferences, and seminars will only reach certain audiences that are already embedded in the ecosystem. More interactive and innovative communication and outreach strategies that effectively disseminate research findings and innovation outcomes are needed to reach stakeholders outside of established academic and industrial circles. Such formats may include workshops, hackathons, and informal dissemination and knowledge sharing events. By employing diverse formats, knowledge transfer becomes more interactive and appealing, increasing awareness and understanding of research and innovation and enhancing interest and trust in science.

Supporting tools: Fairs and conferences, Popular science events

1.4 Funding

A robust and diversified funding landscape with funding for both research and innovation at all stages plays a critical role in supporting scientific advancement and enabling the translation of research into solutions benefitting society. Research grants enable the scientific community to continuously push the boundaries of knowledge while soft funding programmes supports the formation of start-up businesses that drive innovation and entrepreneurship. Funding for later stages, including venture capital and private equity, is central to sustained progress, allowing projects to scale up and transform into tangible solutions with societal impact.

An advanced ecosystem will have both public and private funding available with a varied range of funding streams serving different purposes and supporting different stages in the knowledge valorisation process. The collaboration between different funding bodies is supported by political frameworks that facilitate joint investments and a high level of trust between investors.

Funding not only fuels individual projects but strengthens the entire research ecosystem. By providing financial support for joint initiatives and international collaborations, funding promotes collaboration and knowledge exchange, enhancing the ecosystem's capacity to address societal challenges. As such, funding serves as a critical factor in building a strong research and innovation ecosystem. By supporting collaboration and facilitating innovation, funding is one of the main drivers of the scientific excellence that is necessary to position Europe at the forefront of global research and innovation.

The hallmarks of a solid funding landscape in the ecosystem include:

- **Availability of funding for research**

The development of innovative solutions relies heavily on significant public and private investment for research. Public funding is typically provided by the government and supports fundamental research, infrastructure development, and initiatives that advance strategic societal goals. Private investment from industry and philanthropic organisations often focuses on applied research, technology transfer, and commercialisation of innovations. The availability of both public and private investment ensures a diverse and sustainable funding environment, enabling the ecosystem to flourish.

Supporting tools: Grants and soft funding

- **Availability of funding for innovation and entrepreneurship**

The growth and sustainability of an innovation ecosystem requires funding sources that are practical and efficient. Such funding can come from various sources, including government grants and loans, venture capital, angel investors, and corporate partnerships. It is essential that entrepreneurs can access funds for their entire start-up journey, from pre-seed grants to scaling capital, for the ecosystem to retain the most successful start-ups and reap the full benefits in terms of economic growth, job creation, and the retention of expertise. The availability of funding signals confidence in the ecosystem's potential and allows researchers and innovators to pursue their ideas, develop prototypes, and bring innovations to market.

Supporting tools: Grants and soft funding, Incentivising private investments, Investor society, Startup day/investor networking

- **Visibility/accessibility of grant opportunities**

Having funds available for research and innovation only yields meaningful benefits to the ecosystem if these funds are visible and accessible to the relevant audience. Clearly advertised funding schemes that are available to all qualified applicants are an indicator of a well-functioning funding ecosystem and ensure that the funds to come to their intended use.

In order to reap the full benefits of the funding opportunities available, an advanced ecosystem will often offer application writing assistance in the form of training and other resources to enable researchers and innovators to enhance their skills in grant writing and proposal development. This support can improve the quality of grant applications and increase the chances of securing funding. Additionally, providing guidance on navigating the application process and accessing funding opportunities can make the process more transparent and accessible.

Supporting tools: Funding application support

- **Open, merit-based and transparent grant practices, including constructive feedback on proposals**

Transparency is a fundamental characteristic of a well-functioning funding ecosystem. Clear and well-defined guidelines, criteria, and evaluation processes ensure that funding decisions

are fair and objective. Transparent funding practices enable researchers to understand the expectations, requirements, and review processes associated with different funding opportunities. Evaluation processes should be transparent, rigorous, and focused on assessing the effectiveness and efficiency of the projects. This transparency not only enhances trust but also encourages broader participation, as researchers can make informed decisions about pursuing funding opportunities that align with their research goals and capabilities.

Effective feedback mechanisms greatly benefit researchers by providing constructive feedback on their proposals, regardless of whether they are successful or not. Feedback helps researchers understand the strengths and weaknesses of their proposals, allowing them to refine their ideas and improve future submissions. Moreover, feedback mechanisms contribute to the continuous improvement of the funding process itself, ensuring that evaluation criteria remain relevant and responsive to evolving research and innovation landscapes.

Supporting tools: Funding application support

1.5 Collaboration

Improving knowledge valorisation to address complex challenges requires expertise and perspectives from across the quadruple helix. No single organisation possesses all the necessary knowledge, skills, and resources to tackle the multifaceted problems faced by society today. Through collaboration, the ecosystem can bridge geographic, institutional, and disciplinary differences, leading to scientific and technological advancements to the benefit of society.

Strategic partnerships are a key aspect of collaboration. Such partnerships are forged between different stakeholders, including universities, research institutions, businesses, and public authorities, with the goal of jointly addressing specific research and innovation challenges. Through these partnerships, expertise from different perspectives is combined to tackle problems from multiple angles.

The engagement of policymakers and regulators ensures that research and innovation efforts align with societal needs, and that legal and regulatory frameworks are conducive to the adoption of innovations. By involving policymakers in the collaborative process, the ecosystem can facilitate the translation of research outcomes into policies and actions that can effectively address societal challenges.

The hallmarks of a cohesive collaboration in the ecosystem include:

- **High level of trust and openness between quadruple helix players**

For research and innovation to thrive, it is important to foster a sense of connection and engagement among its stakeholders and participants. To this end, trust and openness are fundamental enablers of open and honest communication, fostering a supportive and collaborative environment. A willingness to share knowledge and expertise further strengthens collaboration, promoting mutual learning and enhancing the overall innovation ecosystem. Through networking events and conferences that facilitate meaningful connections and provide opportunities for interdisciplinary collaboration, it becomes possible to establish

partnerships that contribute to the growth and success of the ecosystem. These collaborations can start as a small, non-committal testing of the waters and develop into more lasting agreements once an alignment of interests has been established.

Sound relationships among academia, industry, and government allows for the incorporation of the unique perspectives and expertise of all partners, enriching the collaborative process and fostering innovation by bringing together different fields of expertise.

Supporting tools: Trust-building activities, Stakeholder engagement forum, Stakeholder engagement platform

- **International orientation**

Enabling foreign collaboration and partnerships with global experts is essential to ensure the international relevance of an innovation and research ecosystem. By actively seeking opportunities for joint research projects and exchange programmes with international counterparts, the ecosystem benefits from diverse perspectives and expertise. This does not only enhance the quality of research but also enable access to new markets and investment opportunities.

Supporting tools: Exchange programmes, Fairs and conferences, Joint research initiatives

- **Shared vision**

A shared vision reflects an alignment of priorities between quadruple helix players, ensuring that the ecosystem will both meet industrial demand and secure societal benefit.

The active involvement of stakeholders representing the industry and the civil society in setting direction for the ecosystem ensures that the research and innovation remain relevant to the needs and demands of the industry and general public. In addition, a close relationship between academia and the industry ensures that the ecosystem will produce talent that is equipped with the skills, knowledge, and experiences sought by employers, ensuring a steady supply of desirable talent.

Supporting tools: Central interest organisation, Industry involvement in university courses

- **Tangible and visible outcomes**

A particular indicator of successful collaboration is the generation of tangible and visible outcomes that demonstrate the value and impact of the collaborative efforts. Such outcomes can include joint research publications, intellectual property development, commercialisation of innovations, policy recommendations, and societal benefits. These outcomes not only validate the success of collaboration and prove the will and ability of the collaboration to go beyond discussions and act on the joint interests, but also contribute to the advancement of knowledge, economic growth, and societal well-being.

Supporting tools: Industry sponsorships, Strategic partnerships

1.6 Governance

The knowledge valorisation in a regional R&I ecosystem benefits from efficient governance. This entails forming robust and respectful relationships between the stakeholders of the quadruple helix. Local, regional and national governments are uniquely able to support research and innovation by creating favourable conditions, e.g. providing infrastructure, streamlining regulatory processes, and offering incentives. By actively engaging with businesses, municipalities and other local authorities can contribute to the growth of prosperous innovation ecosystems, attracting investment, creating jobs, and promoting economic development within their regions.

Another important aspect of efficient governance is the authorities' ability to make informed decisions. Decision-makers need to be knowledgeable about the latest scientific and technological advancements and the strategic implications. This knowledge empowers governments to allocate resources appropriately, develop effective policies, and create an enabling environment for research and innovation. Informed decision-making ensures that investments in research and innovation yield maximum societal and economic benefits.

The hallmarks of efficient governance in the ecosystem include:

- **Long-term joint objectives**

A shared vision and joint long-term objectives enable stakeholders across the quadruple helix to align their efforts and create a stable foundation for research excellence and sustainable innovation. Clear objectives provide direction and ensure that short-term actions contribute to broader societal and economic goals while simultaneously inviting collaboration, enabling consistent policymaking and facilitating long-term investments.

A well-governed knowledge ecosystem continuously refines its joint objectives based on evolving needs, technological advancements, and societal challenges, maintaining relevance and resilience in an ever-changing landscape.

Supporting tools: Central interest organisation, Stakeholder engagement forum

- **Clear definition and recognition of roles and responsibilities**

The involvement of a wide range of stakeholders, including policymakers, researchers, civil society organisations, and citizens, is necessary to ensure that research and innovation activities align with societal needs and values. Open dialogue, consultation processes, and participatory decision-making structures are indicative of inclusive decision-making in the ecosystem.

In this context, a clear definition of roles and responsibilities ensure that all stakeholders understand their contributions, authority, and accountability. By clearly outlining the functions of academia, industry, government, and civil society through a governance framework or code of conduct, ecosystems can avoid duplication of efforts and enhance coordination. Well-defined roles foster efficiency, streamline decision-making, and enable each partner to leverage their strengths.

Supporting tools: Central interest organisation, Stakeholder engagement forum

- **Legitimacy of and trust in decision-makers**

The legitimacy of and trust in the decision-makers in the ERA Hub ensure that the strategic decisions made by e.g. the ERA Hub's board are widely accepted and effectively implemented. Decision-makers must be considered credible, competent, and representative of the ecosystem's various stakeholders to inspire confidence in their leadership. This legitimacy is strengthened by transparent governance frameworks outlining the objectives, priorities, and strategies for knowledge valorisation activities. Implementing monitoring methods to assess the progress, outcomes, and impact of decisions further ensures accountability and strengthens legitimacy, enabling stakeholders to trust that decisions are made in the best interest of the ecosystem rather than for individual or political gain. Additionally, having effective conflict resolution mechanisms in place can help address any disputes or disagreements that may arise among stakeholders and ensure a harmonious and collaborative research environment.

Supporting tools: Commissioned research/analysis for government, Trust-building activities

- **High level of trust in authorities**

A highly functional governance environment is marked by trust in and open collaboration and communication with the authorities. This openness enables an environment where ecosystem players feel safe that the regulatory framework is fair and unbiased and works for the good of society.

Trusted public authorities can also serve as a neutral third party, an important safety net for situations where interpersonal trust fails.

Supporting tools: Commissioned research/analysis for government, Trust-building activities

1.7 Innovation

Within the context of the ERA Hub, innovation is one of the key mechanisms to valorise knowledge through the development of new technologies, products, and services. A well-functioning innovation ecosystem provides a fertile ground for the exploration, development, and application of emerging technologies, enabling the ecosystem to tackle societal challenges and advance industries. This both improves the lives of individuals and enhances the ecosystem's global competitiveness.

An advanced innovation ecosystem will nurture innovative capabilities across the ecosystem. At universities, innovation is embedded in both curricular courses and extracurricular offerings, while researchers are encouraged to explore the commercial potential of their research. Technology transfer offices assist in the management of intellectual property and commercialisation strategy, while in industry, innovation is often a key strategic priority of the business. Similarly, national and local government will set the direction for the development of the area and will often prioritise innovation as a driver of growth, supporting innovation capacity building in society through innovation and entrepreneurship programmes.

In addition to generating new useful solutions, the ecosystem will also benefit from a high level of technology adoption. The widespread uptake of cutting-edge technology enables the ecosystem to

stay at the forefront of scientific advancements and drives the creation of high-value industries and job opportunities. Making the ecosystem an epicentre of innovation-driven entrepreneurship makes it more capable of attracting investments and developing innovative solutions with tangible impact.

The hallmarks of a powerful innovation ecosystem include:

- **Dynamic patent landscape**

A robust culture of intellectual property creation, protection, and commercialisation is characterised by a high volume of filed and granted patents, licensing agreements and strategic partnerships. These activities are indicators of a healthy innovation environment where novel ideas are continuously developed and safeguarded and where innovations move beyond research labs and into real-world applications. In addition, an active patent ecosystem attracts investors and industry collaborators to the ecosystem and encourages competition and collaboration to drive further innovation.

Supporting tools: Innovation hub, Tech transfer office

- **Innovation embedded in education**

An advanced ecosystem will integrate innovation capacity building at all educational levels, particularly at the university. Fostering innovation skills and an entrepreneurial mindset among students is a powerful mechanism to ensure an accumulation of innovative skills that will be carried into the industry and other parts of society upon the students' graduation.

Innovation activities take many shapes, both in the presence of innovation as a recurrent theme in the curricular courses and through extracurricular activities such as hackathons etc. Apart from the skill-building aspect, industry partners may also take advantage of the innovative power of students to generate fresh ideas to solve industry challenges.

Supporting tools: Curricular and/or extracurricular courses in innovation and entrepreneurship, MiniSprint, OpenInnovation, Thematic challenges

- **Prosperous start-up environment**

A thriving start-up environment is characterised by a high level of entrepreneurial activity and start-up formation. Start-ups are often at the forefront of innovation, driven by entrepreneurs who leverage the latest technological developments to address market gaps and advance traditional industries. A high number of start-ups indicates a supportive ecosystem that provides access to funding, mentorship, and resources necessary to establish entrepreneurial ventures. The engagement of the industry illustrates a close alignment between innovation activities and industry needs, while diversity among founders suggest that the ecosystem successfully encourages participation from underrepresented groups and offers an inclusive environment.

An equally important characteristic of the vitality of the ecosystem is the survival rate of the start-ups. A well-established ecosystem will have the resources available to start-ups to support their growth and scaling.

Supporting tools: Innovation hub, Mentorship programmes, Start-up programmes

- **Presence of entrepreneurship infrastructure**

In order to thrive, start-ups and innovators require support to develop, test, and scale their ideas. Incubators and accelerators can offer mentorship, funding opportunities, and business development guidance that help early start-ups grow and navigate the initial challenges. Living labs create real-world testing environments where the start-ups can refine and/or valorise their products and services with direct user feedback, while co-working spaces and innovation hubs enable collaboration, networking, and knowledge exchange between entrepreneurs. Additionally, prototyping facilities, legal support, and commercialisation services are necessary resources for a start-up to transition from concept to marketable solution.

Supporting tools: Innovation hub, Strategic partnerships

- **Presence of innovation intermediaries**

Innovation intermediaries such as innovation hubs, technology transfer offices, and cluster organisations act as connecting points between researchers, entrepreneurs, investors, and policymakers, facilitating knowledge exchange and collaboration within specific industries and driving technological advancements. These central organisations can support the entrepreneurs and facilitate the translation of research findings into useful solutions. Innovation intermediaries can also foster connection within a broader community and can represent the entrepreneurial community in advocating for more streamlined regulatory and administrative frameworks for bringing technological solutions to the wider public.

Supporting tools: Central interest organisation, Innovation Hub, Strategic Partnerships, Tech transfer office

- **Regulatory environment conducive to innovation**

Clear, flexible, and supportive policies that encourage experimentation and growth are indicators of a well-functioning ecosystem. Supportive policies like streamlined business registration processes, simplified intellectual property protections, and tax incentives for research and innovation investments all contribute to reducing barriers for start-ups and established companies alike. Regulatory sandboxes allow emerging technologies to be tested in real-world conditions under regulatory oversight, fostering responsible innovation. Policies that promote open data access, digital transformation, and cross-border collaboration further enhance an ecosystem's ability to adapt to global trends.

Supporting tools: Central interest organisations, Stakeholder engagement forum, Stakeholder engagement platform

Roadmap

As essential drivers of economic growth and societal progress, regional R&I ecosystems must continuously evolve and strive to improve their knowledge valorisation capabilities through the seven lines of action. The COOPERATE Roadmap serves as a guide for regional ecosystems to strategically assess their current state, implement targeted tools to facilitate the improvements, and integrate into a broader network of ERA Hubs to enhance their impact and global competitiveness.

The Roadmap contains guidelines to support regional R&I ecosystems on their journey toward becoming fully developed R&I ecosystems. It offers a **structured process**, outlined in Figure 2 that begins with **engaging key stakeholders** from academia, industry, and government to ensure that efforts are collaborative, leveraging different perspectives and expertise across the quadruple helix. The roadmap encourages the **selection of an initial focus area** and **formation of a core group** and outlines the guidelines on the governance and operation of the ERA Hub. Next, the roadmap invites the ecosystem to **utilise the SELF-ASSESSMENT** to evaluate their current strengths and identify areas for improvement across the seven lines of action. Based on the outcomes of the SELF-ASSESSMENT, the ecosystem will be able to **select appropriate actions from the TOOLBOX** in order to enhance their research outputs, attract and retain talent, improve knowledge transfer mechanisms, strengthen collaboration networks, secure sustainable funding, develop effective governance structures, and foster an environment conducive to innovation. Finally, a core principle of the ERA Hub concept is interconnectedness. The Roadmap recommends **engaging with other ecosystems through the PLATFORM** where ERA Hubs can connect and collaborate. The process is iterative, and the ERA Hub can continuously reapply the SELF-ASSESSMENT to track their progress and select tool appropriate for their continued development.

Figure 2 Illustration of the ERA Hub process to improving maturity, using the COOPERATE tools in an iterative process

By following this roadmap, regional R&I ecosystems can systematically enhance their maturity, strengthen their governance and operational frameworks, and integrate into an EU-wide network of ERA Hubs. Whether an ecosystem is in the early stages of development or already advanced, the

Roadmap serves as a guide for continuous improvement and sustained excellence in research and innovation.

1.8 Gather stakeholders to ensure collaborative effort

Developing an ERA Hub is a collaborative effort, requiring broad participation from across the ecosystem. For this reason, the first action for an ecosystem wishing to advance their maturity and knowledge valorisation capabilities should be to gather the relevant stakeholders from across the quadruple helix in the ecosystem. This entails engaging universities and research institutions, leading representatives from the industry, investors to support research, innovation and other local development, entrepreneurs, innovation intermediaries, local and regional authorities, and preferably organisations representing the civil society. Developing the ERA Hub requires contributions from all stakeholders, and thus establishing a collective desire and long-term commitment to advance the knowledge valorisation in the ecosystem is fundamental for the success of any subsequent initiatives. Within the ERA Hub framework, the central node of the Hub is the university, and it is therefore natural that the university is the driving force behind this first, essential step.

1.9 Determine focus area and establish steering group

Increasing knowledge valorisation in the ecosystem can require different initiatives in different sectors, and in order to streamline efforts, it is recommended to select a focus area. Such a focus area can be industry-related, focusing on e.g. AI or sustainability, or process-related, revolving around e.g. knowledge sharing or policy development across industries. The collected stakeholders should select a focus area that corresponds with the regional ecosystem's strengths and/or strategic goals and should be aligned with national, regional and local priorities to ensure political support. It is recommended to select the most promising area in terms of impact, with the option of developing other areas later in time.

To ensure that ERA Hubs operate efficiently and maintain their momentum, the ERA Hub is governed by a core group consisting of (for instance 4 or 5) members from across the ecosystem, representing varied perspectives and capacities relevant to the selected focus area. The core group can benefit from engaging ecosystem intermediaries to reach and connect with the wider group actors in the ecosystem. The ERA Hub concept and the operational and governing principles are described in further detail in the ERA Hub Framework (D1.4 Final ERA Hub Framework model and KPIs). These guidelines provide ecosystems with frameworks for decision-making, stakeholder engagement, and performance monitoring. The ERA Hub governance model ensures accountability and the ability to respond to emerging challenges and opportunities while maintaining a light and flexible structure.

1.10 Use the SELF-ASSESSMENT to assess starting maturity

In order to determine the starting capacity and the foundation for developing the ERA Hub, the ecosystem stakeholders can benefit from employing the SELF-ASSESSMENT. The SELF-ASSESSMENT is an online resource designed to let ecosystems determine their maturity within each of the seven lines of action. Through a series of questions, the SELF-ASSESSMENT explores the institutions, resources and connections already present in the ecosystem and highlights the regional ecosystem's strengths and areas for improvement. The self-assessment questionnaire goes beyond facts or indicators available in public repositories, aiming to collect more in-depth information that often requires a qualitative

assessment. For this reason, the self-assessment process will be an interactive, co-creative process, based on discussion between different actors in the ecosystem, each bringing their own view on the situation and discussing the underlying reasons or patterns for each topic. By discussing the questions and trying to get to a consensual answer for each of them, the actors will be able to provide a more balanced answer to the question on the situation as is, but also come to a joint understanding of the strengths of the ecosystem and its gaps. For this reason, it is paramount that all stakeholders are represented in the assessment to gain a comprehensive and balanced view of the ecosystem. The SELF-ASSESSMENT will provide a realistic view on the current maturity level of the ecosystem and will help to create a better understanding of the needs and possible actions to further strengthen it. The questionnaire returns an overall maturity score for the ecosystem as well as maturity scores for each line of action, ranging from 1 to 5 in accordance with the model shown in Figure 3:

Figure 3 Maturity scale showing the five levels of maturity from Absence to Collaboration. Adapted from *Leveraging complexity for ecosystemic innovation*, Russel & Smorodinskaya (2018)

- **Absence (level 1)** describes isolated efforts with little or no interaction and communication between players, few and scattered resources, and no governance frameworks in place.
- **Emergence (level 2)** entails early initiatives towards interaction and information sharing between ecosystem players, limited availability or awareness of resources, and inconsistent frameworks.
- **Development (level 3)** describes the alignment of activities between ecosystem players to achieve complementary goals, access to resources and talent, and early international orientation.
- **Diffusion (level 4)** relates to a coordinated effort across ecosystem players, structured and collaborative utilisation of resources, as well as international recognition and talent attraction.
- **Collaboration (level 5)** is the highest level of maturity and entails symbiotic and seamless integration between all quadruple helix players, joint sense of identity and well-defined shared goals, and international innovation leadership.

<i>Mentorship programme</i>	X	X			X
<i>MiniSprint</i>	X	X			X
<i>OpenInnovation</i>	X	X			X
<i>Popular science events</i>	X	X			
<i>Stakeholder engagement forum</i>		X		X	X
<i>Stakeholder engagement platform</i>		X	X		X
<i>Startup day/investor networking</i>	X		X		X
<i>Start-up programmes</i>	X				X
<i>Strategic partnerships</i>	X		X		X
<i>Targeted funding programmes for young talent</i>	X		X		
<i>Technology transfer office</i>		X		X	X
<i>Thematic challenges</i>	X			X	X
<i>Trust-building activities</i>				X	X

Table 1 Overview of which tools pertain to which lines of action

1.12 Connect with other hubs through the PLATFORM

The PLATFORM is an online resource to support ecosystems in their transition to becoming an ERA Hub. The platform is available through the project website and contains four main elements: The present PLAYBOOK, the SELF-ASSESSMENT, the TOOLBOX, and a prototype of a mapping and matching tool.

The mapping and matching tool has two core functions and objectives:

Firstly, it provides information on ERA Hubs across Europe, giving context of their respective strengths and levels of maturity. This will allow ERA Hubs to evaluate how they compare to other hubs both in terms of the overall maturity score, and in terms of maturity within each of the seven lines of action. The second purpose is to facilitate interaction between ERA Hubs to foster collaboration beyond regional and national borders on e.g. joint research projects, strategic partnerships, and international innovation discussions.

Specifically, the mapping and matching tool will detail contact points for each ERA Hub. This initiative is intended to facilitate connection and collaboration between hubs, inviting ecosystems to be inspired by each other and draw on each other's experiences.

This interconnected network strengthens individual ecosystems by fostering cross-border partnerships and creating synergies that accelerate technological advancements and societal impact.

Region: CZ01
Country: Czechia
University: Czech Technical University Prague
Main Contact: Ondrej Durkac - ondrej.durkac@cvut.cz

Organisations in the Hub

Universities:

- [Czech Technical University Prague](#)
- [Charles University](#)
- [Masaryk University](#)
- [University of Life Science Prague](#)
- [Prague University of Economics and Business](#)
- [University of Chemistry and Technology Prague](#)
- [Palacky University Olomouc](#)
- [University of Technology Brno](#)

Research and Technology organisations:

- [Czech Invest](#)

Scope:

The Czech innovation ecosystem is characterised by strong expertise in Engineering, ICT, Advanced Manufacturing and Materials Science. Key fields include Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, Cybersecurity, Nanotechnology and Biotechnology. Application areas focus on Industry 4.0, Automotive & Mobility, Energy & Clean Technologies, Healthcare Innovation and Aerospace.

Short description:

Czech regions focus on advancing Digital Technologies, Smart Manufacturing and Sustainable Innovation

Maturity Score: 2.4

Figure 4 Example of the mapping and matching tool on the PLATFORM

Conclusion and future development

The PLAYBOOK is a guide for ecosystems aiming to improve their maturity and improve knowledge valorisation in the ecosystem. Structured around seven key lines of action—Research, Talent, Knowledge Transfer, Funding, Collaboration, Governance, and Innovation—it provides a robust framework that encompasses vital aspects of ecosystem development. It is the intention that these insights prompt self-evaluation of current strategies and the adoption of new mechanisms to improve knowledge valorisation to the benefit of all. It is the result of a collaborative and inclusive effort across the consortium partners with input from key members of regional R&I ecosystems in Europe.

For the PLAYBOOK to continue to evolve, it, along with the TOOLBOX and SELF-ASSESSMENT, would ideally be continually refined and expanded based on the experiences of real ecosystems using the tools to improve knowledge valorisation. As part of the COOPERATE project, the PLAYBOOK and the other tools will be tested in the second piloting phase in the regions of Lodz (Poland) and Centre-Val-de-Loire (France). The future implementation of the ERA Hub model will require a continuous update of the PLAYBOOK to maintain its relevance, effectiveness and applicability within the evolving European and global research and innovation landscape.

Bibliography

Russell, Martha G., and Nataliya V. Smorodinskaya (2018). Leveraging complexity for ecosystemic innovation. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 136, 114-131.

Appendix A: Practitioner’s version of the PLAYBOOK

(Beginning on next page)

The COOPERATE Playbook

A practical guide to advancing your
research and innovation ecosystem

Funded by
the European Union

COOPERATE

COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production

The partners

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT EINDHOVEN

ČESKÉ VYSOKÉ UČENÍ TECHNICKÉ V PRAZE

STAM

BRAINPORT DEVELOPMENT NV

SCIENCE CITY LYNGBY

DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET

IDEA STRATEGISCHE ECONOMISCHE CONSULTING

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Executive summary

In the current geopolitical landscape with strong global competition and a pressing need for European independence, the translation of Europe's excellent research into real-life solution is more important than ever. The present COOPERATE Playbook is intended as a practical guide to enhancing knowledge valorisation in regional research and innovation (R&I) ecosystems by guiding their transition towards greater maturity. The Playbook revolves around seven lines of action which were identified by the COOPERATE consortium as being central pillars of a strong knowledge creation and valorisation ecosystem. The seven lines of action are Research, Talent, Knowledge transfer, Funding, Collaboration, Governance, and Innovation.

The COOPERATE Playbook highlights the indicators of strength along each line of action, detailing the hallmarks that describe an ideal, advanced level of maturity within regional knowledge ecosystems. Designed for ecosystem actors across the quadruple helix, meaning both universities and research organisations, the industry, public administration and policymakers, and NGOs representing the civil society, the COOPERATE Playbook describes the factors that are typically present in advanced ecosystems, contributing to their success.

In addition, the COOPERATE Playbook offers a Roadmap to guide emerging regional ecosystems towards greater maturity in their process of becoming an ERA Hub. This roadmap offers a step-by-step guide for ecosystems to engage the relevant stakeholders and begin the journey towards becoming an ERA Hub. The roadmap introduces the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool that can help regional ecosystems gauge their existing levels of maturity and the COOPERATE Toolbox containing 33 tried-and-true tools consolidating the consortium's collective expertise and leveraging best practice models that ecosystems can implement to improve their level of maturity. Finally, the roadmap introduces the COOPERATE Platform through which aspiring and existing ERA Hubs can connect, collaborate and access resources to support their development.

The COOPERATE Playbook, Self-Assessment Digital Tool, Toolbox and Platform have all been co-developed with and validated by key stakeholders through a series of co-creation sessions.

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List of abbreviations

ACRONYM	STANDS FOR
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
R&I	Research & Innovation

Introduction

The European Union (EU) boasts a wealth of world-class research but lags behind its global competitors when it comes to translating this knowledge into practical solutions that benefit the wider society. In today's rapidly evolving geopolitical landscape, Europe's ability to withstand global pressure and competition has become a top priority. The present COOPERATE Playbook (hereinafter: the PLAYBOOK) is intended as a practical guide to assist ecosystems – European Research Area (ERA) Hubs - through their transition towards greater maturity. An ERA Hub is an ecosystem dedicated to improving knowledge valorisation, specifically defined in the COOPERATE project as follows:

“An ERA Hub is an ecosystem of quadruple helix actors led by universities aiming at improving knowledge valorisation within their region.”

The ERA Hub concept is described in greater detail in the ERA Hub Framework.

The PLAYBOOK is designed for ecosystem actors across the quadruple helix, including academia, industry, public administration and the civil society. The PLAYBOOK describes the hallmarks of excellence along seven lines of action: Research, Talent, Knowledge transfer, Funding, Collaboration, Governance, and Innovation.

In addition, the PLAYBOOK offers a Roadmap to guide ERA Hubs towards greater maturity. This roadmap introduces the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool (hereinafter: the SELF-ASSESSMENT) that can help ecosystems gauge their existing levels of maturity, and the COOPERATE Toolbox (hereinafter: the TOOLBOX) containing 33 concrete tools that the ecosystem can implement to improve their level of maturity. Finally, the roadmap introduces the COOPERATE Platform (hereinafter: the PLATFORM) through which aspiring and existing ERA Hubs can connect and access resources (including the COOPERATE tools) to support their development.

The PLAYBOOK was developed by the Technical University of Denmark based on observable traits of advanced regional R&I ecosystems. Both the PLAYBOOK, SELF-ASSESSMENT, TOOLBOX and PLATFORM have been co-developed with and validated by key stakeholders through a series of co-creation sessions.

Lines of action

This chapter details each of the seven lines of action, including the hallmarks of excellence that describe an ideal, advanced level of maturity. This model shows the seven lenses through which maturity is viewed in the ERA Hub framework and make up the foundation of the SELF-ASSESSMENT and the TOOLBOX.

Figure 1 Illustration of the seven lines of action defined in the cooperate project: Research, Talent, Knowledge transfer, Funding, Collaboration, Governance and Innovation

The **Research** line of action is concerned with the contextual conditions that are required to ensure a sufficiently level of high-quality research outputs. It relates to the creation of an environment that enables scientific

exploration, promoting interdisciplinarity and collaboration and strengthening research infrastructure. The production of high-quality knowledge is a fundamental prerequisite for knowledge valorisation.

Talent focuses on the critical aspect of developing, attracting and retaining top-tier research and innovation professionals, including the implementation of strategies for fostering talent development, promoting diversity and inclusion and establishing attractive career paths and living conditions. Highly skilled professionals are essential drivers of the production and valorisation of knowledge.

Knowledge transfer is a central element of knowledge valorisation and pertains to the creation of trusting relationships between ecosystem players, establishing solid knowledge transfer infrastructure and actively supporting knowledge transfer and dissemination through engaging activities. Sound mechanisms for knowledge transfer facilitate knowledge valorisation by ensuring that the knowledge is accessed by the institutions and people capable of translating them into real-life solutions benefiting society.

Through the **Funding** line of action, the ecosystem must ensure that the available funding is sufficient to support both research and innovation in the ecosystem as well as ensuring the visibility and accessibility of funds and ensuring fairness and trust through transparent and merit-based grant practices. The availability of funding is fundamental to all initiatives within knowledge production and valorisation.

Collaboration is a cornerstone of successful ecosystem development, revolving around trust, openness to collaboration both internally in the ecosystem and internationally. It highlights the importance of shared goals and visions to drive tangible outcomes. Interconnectedness is a core element of knowledge valorisation as it allows the ecosystem to combine expertise and resources.

Governance structures ensure the sustainability and long-term success of ecosystem initiatives by promoting transparency, accountability, and fostering trust among stakeholders. This line of action addresses the need for legitimacy among decision-makers to ensure continued support for the activities of the ecosystem. Sound governance enables the establishment and implementation of joint goals within knowledge valorisation.

The **Innovation** line of action emphasises the need for a dynamic patent landscape, a nurturing environment for entrepreneurs, innovation infrastructure and intermediaries and a regulatory environment that support knowledge valorisation through innovation. Innovation and entrepreneurship are perhaps the most tangible forms of knowledge valorisation, directly translating the science and technology of the ecosystem into real-life solutions to society's problems.

In the sections below, each line of action is described in more detail, including the hallmarks of excellence that are indicative of advanced maturity. Each hallmark is supported by a number of tools that the ERA Hub can employ to advance their maturity in that particular respect. The tools are described in the TOOLBOX.

Research

Research makes up the foundation of both the broader ERA initiative and the ERA Hub concept, specifically. The production of world-class research drives the development of solutions to societal problems, generating workplaces and economic growth while strengthening the ecosystem's reputation and ability to attract talent. For the research ecosystem to ensure the sustained support of the wider public, it is necessary to promote transparency, accountability, and public engagement in the research process. This can be achieved through inviting open dialogue and communicating the societal relevance of research.

The hallmarks of a prosperous research ecosystem include:

Presence of **large** research and technology institutions

Universities and research centres are the primary drivers of research and serve as focal points for advanced research and technology development. These institutions bring together experts and state-of-the-art facilities, providing a nurturing environment for interdisciplinary collaboration and the pursuit of transformative breakthroughs. The presence of multiple large research and technology institutions enhances the overall research output and contributes to the ecosystem's reputation.

Supporting tools: Centres of excellence, Industry sponsorships

Link to research infrastructure

Producing world-class science requires access to world-class research infrastructure, such as laboratories, scientific instrumentation and technologies, data resources, and computational tools. An advanced ecosystem is characterised by investment in research infrastructure and equipment to increase the research capacity of the ecosystem. This equipment can be present in the ecosystem itself or, in the case of particularly complex, specialised, or expensive infrastructure, it can be accessed through collaborations with other ecosystems or scientific institutions (e.g. the Large Hadron Collider at CERN).

Supporting tools: Strategic partnerships, Industry sponsorships

Diversity of research areas

The exploration of a diverse range of research areas supports interdisciplinary collaboration and fosters cross-pollination across science, engineering, and technology. This interdisciplinarity, particularly when further combined with social sciences and humanities, enables the ecosystem to creatively address a broad spectrum of research areas and develop comprehensive solutions to complex problems. This broad research capacity is generally reflected in the presence of a high number of faculties, institutes and research groups and contributes to the ecosystem's richness and relevance.

Supporting tools: Joint research initiatives, Industrial PhD

Continuous publication of high-quality science

The consistent publication of high-quality science with high impact strengthens the ecosystem's influence and recognition within the scientific community. Research excellence is supported in an environment that enables research over longer time horizons and with sustained funding, as these extended projects allow for the thorough investigation that enables breakthrough discoveries.

Successful research ecosystems will place the strongest emphasis on research ethics and integrity to ensure the credibility and trustworthiness of research outcomes and ensure this through policies and guidelines that promote responsible conduct of research, data integrity, and transparent reporting.

Supporting tools: Commissioned research for industry, Commissioned research/analysis for government

Talent

Talent plays a central role in driving progress and ensuring adaptability in the ever-changing landscape of research and innovation. A diverse and well-developed talent pool will ensure robustness of the ecosystem and propel the creation and valorisation of knowledge, ultimately leading to sustainable progress and societal impact.

Nurturing talent through education is a cornerstone of ensuring the research and innovation capabilities required for the ecosystem to grow and develop a reputation for excellence. Through life-long education, both students and professionals are equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills to thrive in the research and innovation landscape.

In addition to developing home-grown talent, attracting and retaining talented individuals from outside the ecosystem is key. In order to be attractive to international top talent, the ecosystem must offer access to impactful research projects, state-of-the-art facilities, and funding opportunities in addition to attractive living

conditions. Attracting diverse talent from different demographics and backgrounds is expected to foster greater creativity and innovation.

The hallmarks of strong talent development and retention in the ecosystem include:

Ability to develop talent

An advanced talent ecosystem will emphasise education in order to develop a rich talent pool and a culture of learning, facilitating collaboration, knowledge exchange, and cross-pollination of ideas. The central node of the education landscape is the university, providing students and professionals with the skills and knowledge to excel in their respective fields through high-quality study programmes and life-long learning opportunities. These educational programmes are often co-developed with the local industry and designed to meet the demands of the employers to ensure both availability of talent and a high level of employment.

However, the educational institutions in the ecosystem should support the entirety of an individual's career. This spans early education, where early initiatives encourage children and young students from underrepresented backgrounds to pursue careers within research and innovation, degree programmes that are aligned with the needs of the ecosystem, and offering opportunities for continuous learning throughout the career.

In addition to formal education, mentorship programmes are powerful mechanisms to ensure both effective knowledge transfer and continuous development of the talent body. Mentorship networks connect experienced professionals with emerging researchers and innovators, providing guidance, support, and connections to accelerate the individual's learning and growth and increase the research and innovation capacity of the ecosystem as a whole.

Supporting tools: Career fair, Diversity outreach, Industry involvement in university courses, Mentorship programme

Ability to attract talent from outside the ecosystem

The ability to attract talent from outside the boundaries of the ecosystem – both students and employees – demonstrates a reputation for excellence and a dedication to making the ecosystem an attractive destination for top talent. This interregional and international interest is typically a result of high-quality educational programmes, attractive workplaces with impactful research and funding opportunities, and an inclusive and welcoming living environment. The ecosystem should provide support to help international talent find

affordable housing and childcare, integrate into the local community, and navigate cultural differences to help them and their families settle into the ecosystem.

The presence of talent coming from different cultural backgrounds fosters innovation and knowledge exchange and forges connections with other ecosystems, which in turn is expected to attract further talent from outside the ecosystem.

Supporting tools: Attractive living conditions, Exchange programmes

Ability to retain local and international talent

The retention of top talent in the ecosystem is as important as developing and attracting this talent in the first place. This requires both attractive opportunities for career development, a culture that recognises and rewards excellence, and a high quality of life in the ecosystem, enabling the long-term engagement of expert professionals who contribute to the growth and success of the ecosystem.

Supporting tools: Industry-sponsored prizes, Targeted funding programmes for young talent

Critical mass of scientific personnel

The presence of a significant number of skilled researchers, innovators and entrepreneurs within the ecosystem is a marker of a critical mass of talent in the ecosystem. A high concentration of talent enables the ecosystem to produce world-class work and further attract and retain top talent, thereby strengthening the research capacity for the ecosystem.

Supporting tools: Attractive living conditions

Dynamic job market with opportunities for career development across quadruple helix

The opportunities for employees to develop their career and achieve international recognition is key to attracting top talent. A large number of companies and research institutions paired with a low level of unemployment for scientific personnel are indicators of a career landscape that allows researchers and innovators can find fulfilling career prospects.

Opportunities for continued education and training, participation in joint projects and the mobility of employees between employers across the quadruple helix strengthen the basis for collaboration, knowledge transfer and the development of best practices between ecosystem players.

Supporting tools: Exchange programmes, Joint research activities

Knowledge transfer

Knowledge transfer is at the heart of a strong research and innovation ecosystem. Sound technology transfer mechanisms ensure that scientific developments are applied in real-world contexts and accelerates societal development. Ensuring this flow of knowledge, expertise, and technology can lead to the development of new industries, job creation, and economic growth.

In addition to the application of technologies in real-life settings, knowledge transfer to the public ensures that research outcomes are accessible to a wider audience. Collaboration and dialogue with the public not only democratises knowledge but also helps build trust within the general population by showcasing relatable societal progress brought about by research and innovation.

One of the subtle yet powerful conductors of knowledge transfer are university students. As the students acquire knowledge, they also have the potential to disseminate it effectively into society. This can be through informal settings among family and friends or through their dispersion into the workforce after completing their studies. By fostering an inclusive and engaging learning environment, the students become integral to the research and innovation ecosystem, actively bridging the gap between academia and society.

The hallmarks of efficient knowledge transfer in the ecosystem include:

Well-established relationships between ecosystem players

Advanced regional knowledge and innovation ecosystems often enjoy a high level of trust, transparency, integrity, and accountability, resulting in strong partnerships between academia, industry, government, and non-profit organisations.

Trusting relationships between ecosystem players are key to ensuring efficient knowledge sharing. Trust is fundamental for open knowledge sharing as it enables ecosystem members to share ideas without fearing that it will harm their business. Additionally, trust gives stakeholders confidence in the credibility and reliability of the knowledge being transferred.

Besides trust, transparency around who to talk to in the ecosystem, relationship anchor points in the organisations and openness to welcome new members into the ecosystem are indicators of healthy knowledge transfer relationships in an ecosystem.

Supporting tools: Central interest organisation, Stakeholder engagement forum, Stakeholder engagement platform

Effective knowledge transfer infrastructure internally in ecosystem and outside ecosystem

An ecosystem with efficient knowledge transfer will have mechanisms such as joint research projects and industry-academic partnerships to ensure knowledge transfer both among the ecosystem players and between the ecosystem and the outside world. In addition, the mobility of students and employees through joint research initiatives and exchange programmes promote talent exchange and cross-cultural learning, and partnerships with researchers and organisations from around the world facilitate knowledge transfer, collaboration, and the sharing of best practices.

Open science practices, including open access publishing, sharing of research data, and collaboration on open-source projects maximise the visibility and impact of the research from the ecosystem. A culture of transparency, reproducibility, and sharing within the ecosystem facilitates collaboration, and accelerates the pace of scientific progress.

Supporting tools: Exchange programmes, Joint research projects, Tech transfer office

Engaging knowledge transfer activities

Knowledge sharing and knowledge transfer can be facilitated through events and activities that engage different players in the ecosystem, including the general public. Engaging knowledge sharing and dissemination formats are essential in order to capture the attention and interest of stakeholders. Traditional modes of dissemination, such as academic papers, conferences, and seminars will only reach certain audiences that are already embedded in the ecosystem. More interactive and innovative communication and outreach strategies that effectively disseminate research findings and innovation outcomes are needed to reach stakeholders outside of established academic and industrial circles. Such formats may include workshops, hackathons, and informal dissemination and knowledge sharing events. By employing diverse formats, knowledge transfer becomes more interactive and appealing, increasing awareness and understanding of research and innovation and enhancing interest and trust in science.

Supporting tools: Fairs and conferences, Popular science events

Funding

A robust and diversified funding landscape with funding for both research and innovation at all stages plays a critical role in supporting scientific advancement and enabling the translation of research into solutions benefitting society. Research grants enable the scientific community to continuously push the boundaries of knowledge while soft funding programmes supports the formation of start-up businesses that drive innovation

and entrepreneurship. Funding for later stages, including venture capital and private equity, is central to sustained progress, allowing projects to scale up and transform into tangible solutions with societal impact.

An advanced ecosystem will have both public and private funding available with a varied range of funding streams serving different purposes and supporting different stages in the knowledge valorisation process. The collaboration between different funding bodies is supported by political frameworks that facilitate joint investments and a high level of trust between investors.

Funding not only fuels individual projects but strengthens the entire research ecosystem. By providing financial support for joint initiatives and international collaborations, funding promotes collaboration and knowledge exchange, enhancing the ecosystem's capacity to address societal challenges. As such, funding serves as a critical factor in building a strong research and innovation ecosystem. By supporting collaboration and facilitating innovation, funding is one of the main drivers of the scientific excellence that is necessary to position Europe at the forefront of global research and innovation.

The hallmarks of a solid funding landscape in the ecosystem include:

Availability of funding for research

The development of innovative solutions relies heavily on significant public and private investment for research. Public funding is typically provided by the government and supports fundamental research, infrastructure development, and initiatives that advance strategic societal goals. Private investment from industry and philanthropic organisations often focuses on applied research, technology transfer, and commercialisation of innovations. The availability of both public and private investment ensures a diverse and sustainable funding environment, enabling the ecosystem to flourish.

Supporting tools: Grants and soft funding

Availability of funding for innovation and entrepreneurship

The growth and sustainability of an innovation ecosystem requires funding sources that are practical and efficient. Such funding can come from various sources, including government grants and loans, venture capital, angel investors, and corporate partnerships. It is essential that entrepreneurs can access funds for their entire start-up journey, from pre-seed grants to scaling capital, for the ecosystem to retain the most successful start-ups and reap the full benefits in terms of economic growth, job creation, and the retention of expertise. The availability of funding signals confidence in the ecosystem's potential and allows researchers and innovators to pursue their ideas, develop prototypes, and bring innovations to market.

Supporting tools: Grants and soft funding, Incentivising private investments, Investor society, Startup day/investor networking

Visibility/accessibility of grant opportunities

Having funds available for research and innovation only yields meaningful benefits to the ecosystem if these funds are visible and accessible to the relevant audience. Clearly advertised funding schemes that are available to all qualified applicants are an indicator of a well-functioning funding ecosystem and ensure that the funds come to their intended use.

In order to reap the full benefits of the funding opportunities available, an advanced ecosystem will often offer application writing assistance in the form of training and other resources to enable researchers and innovators to enhance their skills in grant writing and proposal development. This support can improve the quality of grant applications and increase the chances of securing funding. Additionally, providing guidance on navigating the application process and accessing funding opportunities can make the process more transparent and accessible.

Supporting tools: Funding application support

Open, merit-based and transparent grant practices, including constructive feedback on proposals

Transparency is a fundamental characteristic of a well-functioning funding ecosystem. Clear and well-defined guidelines, criteria, and evaluation processes ensure that funding decisions are fair and objective. Transparent funding practices enable researchers to understand the expectations, requirements, and review processes associated with different funding opportunities. Evaluation processes should be transparent, rigorous, and focused on assessing the effectiveness and efficiency of the projects. This transparency not only enhances trust but also encourages broader participation, as researchers can make informed decisions about pursuing funding opportunities that align with their research goals and capabilities.

Effective feedback mechanisms greatly benefit researchers by providing constructive feedback on their proposals, regardless of whether they are successful or not. Feedback helps researchers understand the strengths and weaknesses of their proposals, allowing them to refine their ideas and improve future submissions. Moreover, feedback mechanisms contribute to the continuous improvement of the funding process itself, ensuring that evaluation criteria remain relevant and responsive to evolving research and innovation landscapes.

Supporting tools: Funding application support

Collaboration

Improving knowledge valorisation to address complex challenges requires expertise and perspectives from across the quadruple helix. No single organisation possesses all the necessary knowledge, skills, and resources to tackle the multifaceted problems faced by society today. Through collaboration, the ecosystem can bridge geographic, institutional, and disciplinary differences, leading to scientific and technological advancements to the benefit of society.

Strategic partnerships are a key aspect of collaboration. Such partnerships are forged between different stakeholders, including universities, research institutions, businesses, and public authorities, with the goal of jointly addressing specific research and innovation challenges. Through these partnerships, expertise from different perspectives is combined to tackle problems from multiple angles.

The engagement of policymakers and regulators ensures that research and innovation efforts align with societal needs, and that legal and regulatory frameworks are conducive to the adoption of innovations. By involving policymakers in the collaborative process, the ecosystem can facilitate the translation of research outcomes into policies and actions that can effectively address societal challenges.

The hallmarks of a cohesive collaboration in the ecosystem include:

High level of trust and openness between quadruple helix players

For research and innovation to thrive, it is important to foster a sense of connection and engagement among its stakeholders and participants. To this end, trust and openness are fundamental enablers of open and honest communication, fostering a supportive and collaborative environment. A willingness to share knowledge and expertise further strengthens collaboration, promoting mutual learning and enhancing the overall innovation ecosystem. Through networking events and conferences that facilitate meaningful connections and provide opportunities for interdisciplinary collaboration, it becomes possible to establish partnerships that contribute to the growth and success of the ecosystem. These collaborations can start as a small, non-committal testing of the waters and develop into more lasting agreements once an alignment of interests has been established.

Sound relationships among academia, industry, and government allows for the incorporation of the unique perspectives and expertise of all partners, enriching the collaborative process and fostering innovation by bringing together different fields of expertise.

Supporting tools: Trust-building activities, Stakeholder engagement forum, Stakeholder engagement platform

International orientation

Enabling foreign collaboration and partnerships with global experts is essential to ensure the international relevance of an innovation and research ecosystem. By actively seeking opportunities for joint research projects and exchange programmes with international counterparts, the ecosystem benefits from diverse perspectives and expertise. This does not only enhance the quality of research but also enable access to new markets and investment opportunities.

Supporting tools: Exchange programmes, Fairs and conferences, Joint research initiatives

Shared vision

A shared vision reflects an alignment of priorities between quadruple helix players, ensuring that the ecosystem will both meet industrial demand and secure societal benefit.

The active involvement of stakeholders representing the industry and the civil society in setting direction for the ecosystem ensures that the research and innovation remain relevant to the needs and demands of the industry and general public. In addition, a close relationship between academia and the industry ensures that the ecosystem will produce talent that is equipped with the skills, knowledge, and experiences sought by employers, ensuring a steady supply of desirable talent.

Supporting tools: Central interest organisation, Industry involvement in university courses

Tangible and visible outcomes

A particular indicator of successful collaboration is the generation of tangible and visible outcomes that demonstrate the value and impact of the collaborative efforts. Such outcomes can include joint research publications, intellectual property development, commercialisation of innovations, policy recommendations, and societal benefits. These outcomes not only validate the success of collaboration and prove the will and ability of the collaboration to go beyond discussions and act on the joint interests, but also contribute to the advancement of knowledge, economic growth, and societal well-being.

Supporting tools: Industry sponsorships, Strategic partnerships

Governance

The knowledge valorisation in a regional R&I ecosystem benefits from efficient governance. This entails forming robust and respectful relationships between the stakeholders of the quadruple helix. Local, regional and national governments are uniquely able to support research and innovation by creating favourable conditions, e.g.

providing infrastructure, streamlining regulatory processes, and offering incentives. By actively engaging with businesses, municipalities and other local authorities can contribute to the growth of prosperous innovation ecosystems, attracting investment, creating jobs, and promoting economic development within their regions. Another important aspect of efficient governance is the authorities' ability to make informed decisions. Decision-makers need to be knowledgeable about the latest scientific and technological advancements and the strategic implications. This knowledge empowers governments to allocate resources appropriately, develop effective policies, and create an enabling environment for research and innovation. Informed decision-making ensures that investments in research and innovation yield maximum societal and economic benefits.

The hallmarks of efficient governance in the ecosystem include:

Long-term joint objectives

A shared vision and joint long-term objectives enable stakeholders across the quadruple helix to align their efforts and create a stable foundation for research excellence and sustainable innovation. Clear objectives provide direction and ensure that short-term actions contribute to broader societal and economic goals while simultaneously inviting collaboration, enabling consistent policymaking and facilitating long-term investments. A well-governed knowledge ecosystem continuously refines its joint objectives based on evolving needs, technological advancements, and societal challenges, maintaining relevance and resilience in an ever-changing landscape.

Supporting tools: Central interest organisation, Stakeholder engagement forum

Clear definition and recognition of roles and responsibilities

The involvement of a wide range of stakeholders, including policymakers, researchers, civil society organisations, and citizens, is necessary to ensure that research and innovation activities align with societal needs and values. Open dialogue, consultation processes, and participatory decision-making structures are indicative of inclusive decision-making in the ecosystem.

In this context, a clear definition of roles and responsibilities ensure that all stakeholders understand their contributions, authority, and accountability. By clearly outlining the functions of academia, industry, government, and civil society through a governance framework or code of conduct, ecosystems can avoid duplication of efforts and enhance coordination. Well-defined roles foster efficiency, streamline decision-making, and enable each partner to leverage their strengths.

Supporting tools: Central interest organisation, Stakeholder engagement forum

Legitimacy of and trust in decision-makers

The legitimacy of and trust in the decision-makers in the ERA Hub ensure that the strategic decisions made by e.g. the ERA Hub's board are widely accepted and effectively implemented. Decision-makers must be considered credible, competent, and representative of the ecosystem's various stakeholders to inspire confidence in their leadership. This legitimacy is strengthened by transparent governance frameworks outlining the objectives, priorities, and strategies for knowledge valorisation activities. Implementing monitoring methods to assess the progress, outcomes, and impact of decisions further ensures accountability and strengthens legitimacy, enabling stakeholders to trust that decisions are made in the best interest of the ecosystem rather than for individual or political gain. Additionally, having effective conflict resolution mechanisms in place can help address any disputes or disagreements that may arise among stakeholders and ensure a harmonious and collaborative research environment.

Supporting tools: Commissioned research/analysis for government, Trust-building activities

High level of trust in authorities

A highly functional governance environment is marked by trust in and open collaboration and communication with the authorities. This openness enables an environment where ecosystem players feel safe that the regulatory framework is fair and unbiased and works for the good of society.

Trusted public authorities can also serve as a neutral third party, an important safety net for situations where interpersonal trust fails.

Supporting tools: Commissioned research/analysis for government, Trust-building activities

Innovation

Within the context of the ERA Hub, innovation is one of the key mechanisms to valorise knowledge through the development of new technologies, products, and services. A well-functioning innovation ecosystem provides a fertile ground for the exploration, development, and application of emerging technologies, enabling the ecosystem to tackle societal challenges and advance industries. This both improves the lives of individuals and enhances the ecosystem's global competitiveness.

An advanced innovation ecosystem will nurture innovative capabilities across the ecosystem. At universities, innovation is embedded in both curricular courses and extracurricular offerings, while researchers are encouraged to explore the commercial potential of their research. Technology transfer offices assist in the

management of intellectual property and commercialisation strategy, while in industry, innovation is often a key strategic priority of the business. Similarly, national and local government will set the direction for the development of the area and will often prioritise innovation as a driver of growth, supporting innovation capacity building in society through innovation and entrepreneurship programmes.

In addition to generating new useful solutions, the ecosystem will also benefit from a high level of technology adoption. The widespread uptake of cutting-edge technology enables the ecosystem to stay at the forefront of scientific advancements and drives the creation of high-value industries and job opportunities. Making the ecosystem an epicentre of innovation-driven entrepreneurship makes it more capable of attracting investments and developing innovative solutions with tangible impact.

The hallmarks of a powerful innovation ecosystem include:

Dynamic patent landscape

A robust culture of intellectual property creation, protection, and commercialisation is characterised by a high volume of filed and granted patents, licensing agreements and strategic partnerships. These activities are indicators of a healthy innovation environment where novel ideas are continuously developed and safeguarded and where innovations move beyond research labs and into real-world applications. In addition, an active patent ecosystem attracts investors and industry collaborators to the ecosystem and encourages competition and collaboration to drive further innovation.

Supporting tools: Innovation hub, Tech transfer office

Innovation embedded in education

An advanced ecosystem will integrate innovation capacity building at all educational levels, particularly at the university. Fostering innovation skills and an entrepreneurial mindset among students is a powerful mechanism to ensure an accumulation of innovative skills that will be carried into the industry and other parts of society upon the students' graduation.

Innovation activities take many shapes, both in the presence of innovation as a recurrent theme in the curricular courses and through extracurricular activities such as hackathons etc. Apart from the skill-building aspect, industry partners may also take advantage of the innovative power of students to generate fresh ideas to solve industry challenges.

Supporting tools: Curricular and/or extracurricular courses in innovation and entrepreneurship,

MiniSprint, OpenInnovation, Thematic challenges

Prosperous start-up environment

A thriving start-up environment is characterised by a high level of entrepreneurial activity and start-up formation. Start-ups are often at the forefront of innovation, driven by entrepreneurs who leverage the latest technological developments to address market gaps and advance traditional industries. A high number of start-ups indicates a supportive ecosystem that provides access to funding, mentorship, and resources necessary to establish entrepreneurial ventures. The engagement of the industry illustrates a close alignment between innovation activities and industry needs, while diversity among founders suggest that the ecosystem successfully encourages participation from underrepresented groups and offers an inclusive environment.

An equally important characteristic of the vitality of the ecosystem is the survival rate of the start-ups. A well-established ecosystem will have the resources available to start-ups to support their growth and scaling.

Supporting tools: Innovation hub, Mentorship programmes, Start-up programmes

Presence of entrepreneurship infrastructure

In order to thrive, start-ups and innovators require support to develop, test, and scale their ideas. Incubators and accelerators can offer mentorship, funding opportunities, and business development guidance that help early start-ups grow and navigate the initial challenges. Living labs create real-world testing environments where the start-ups can refine and/or valorise their products and services with direct user feedback, while co-working spaces and innovation hubs enable collaboration, networking, and knowledge exchange between entrepreneurs. Additionally, prototyping facilities, legal support, and commercialisation services are necessary resources for a start-up to transition from concept to marketable solution.

Supporting tools: Innovation hub, Strategic partnerships

Presence of innovation intermediaries

Innovation intermediaries such as innovation hubs, technology transfer offices, and cluster organisations act as connecting points between researchers, entrepreneurs, investors, and policymakers, facilitating knowledge exchange and collaboration within specific industries and driving technological advancements. These central organisations can support the entrepreneurs and facilitate the translation of research findings into useful solutions. Innovation intermediaries can also foster connection within a broader community and can represent the entrepreneurial community in advocating for more streamlined regulatory and administrative frameworks for bringing technological solutions to the wider public.

Supporting tools: Central interest organisation, Innovation Hub, Strategic Partnerships, Tech transfer office

Regulatory environment conducive to innovation

Clear, flexible, and supportive policies that encourage experimentation and growth are indicators of a well-functioning ecosystem. Supportive policies like streamlined business registration processes, simplified intellectual property protections, and tax incentives for research and innovation investments all contribute to reducing barriers for start-ups and established companies alike. Regulatory sandboxes allow emerging technologies to be tested in real-world conditions under regulatory oversight, fostering responsible innovation. Policies that promote open data access, digital transformation, and cross-border collaboration further enhance an ecosystem's ability to adapt to global trends.

Supporting tools: Central interest organisations, Stakeholder engagement forum, Stakeholder engagement platform

Roadmap

As essential drivers of economic growth and societal progress, regional R&I ecosystems must continuously evolve and strive to improve their knowledge valorisation capabilities through the seven lines of action. The COOPERATE Roadmap serves as a guide for regional ecosystems to strategically assess their current state, implement targeted tools to facilitate the improvements, and integrate into a broader network of ERA Hubs to enhance their impact and global competitiveness.

The Roadmap contains guidelines to support regional R&I ecosystems on their journey toward becoming fully developed R&I ecosystems. It offers a **structured process**, outlined in Figure 2 that begins with **engaging key stakeholders** from academia, industry, and government to ensure that efforts are collaborative, leveraging different perspectives and expertise across the quadruple helix. The roadmap encourages the **selection of an initial focus area** and **formation of a core group** and outlines the guidelines on the governance and operation of the ERA Hub. Next, the roadmap invites the ecosystem to **utilise the SELF-ASSESSMENT** to evaluate their current strengths and identify areas for improvement across the seven lines of action. Based on the outcomes of the SELF-ASSESSMENT, the ecosystem will be able to **select appropriate actions from the TOOLBOX** in order to enhance their research outputs, attract and retain talent, improve knowledge transfer mechanisms, strengthen collaboration networks, secure sustainable funding, develop effective governance structures, and foster an environment conducive to innovation. Finally, a core principle of the ERA Hub concept is interconnectedness. The Roadmap recommends **engaging with other ecosystems through the PLATFORM** where ERA Hubs can connect and collaborate. The process is iterative, and the ERA Hub can continuously reapply the SELF-ASSESSMENT to track their progress and select tool appropriate for their continued development.

Figure 2 Illustration of the ERA Hub process to improving maturity, using the COOPERATE tools in an iterative process

By following this roadmap, regional R&I ecosystems can systematically enhance their maturity, strengthen their governance and operational frameworks, and integrate into an EU-wide network of ERA Hubs. Whether an ecosystem is in the early stages of development or already advanced, the Roadmap serves as a guide for continuous improvement and sustained excellence in research and innovation.

Gather stakeholders to ensure collaborative effort

Developing an ERA Hub is a collaborative effort, requiring broad participation from across the ecosystem. For this reason, the first action for an ecosystem wishing to advance their maturity and knowledge valorisation capabilities should be to gather the relevant stakeholders from across the quadruple helix in the ecosystem. This entails engaging universities and research institutions, leading representatives from the industry, investors to support research, innovation and other local development, entrepreneurs, innovation intermediaries, local and regional authorities, and preferably organisations representing the civil society. Developing the ERA Hub requires contributions from all stakeholders, and thus establishing a collective desire and long-term

commitment to advance the knowledge valorisation in the ecosystem is fundamental for the success of any subsequent initiatives.

Within the ERA Hub framework, the central node of the Hub is the university, and it is therefore natural that the university is the driving force behind this first, essential step.

Determine focus area and establish steering group

Increasing knowledge valorisation in the ecosystem can require different initiatives in different sectors, and in order to streamline efforts, it is recommended to select a focus area. Such a focus area can be industry-related, focusing on e.g. AI or sustainability, or process-related, revolving around e.g. knowledge sharing or policy development across industries. The collected stakeholders should select a focus area that corresponds with the regional ecosystem's strengths and/or strategic goals and should be aligned with national, regional and local priorities to ensure political support. It is recommended to select the most promising area in terms of impact, with the option of developing other areas later in time.

To ensure that ERA Hubs operate efficiently and maintain their momentum, the ERA Hub is governed by a core group consisting of (for instance 4 or 5) members from across the ecosystem, representing varied perspectives and capacities relevant to the selected focus area. The core group can benefit from engaging ecosystem intermediaries to reach and connect with the wider group actors in the ecosystem. The ERA Hub concept and the operational and governing principles are described in further detail in the ERA Hub Framework. These guidelines provide ecosystems with frameworks for decision-making, stakeholder engagement, and performance monitoring. The ERA Hub governance model ensures accountability and the ability to respond to emerging challenges and opportunities while maintaining a light and flexible structure.

Use the SELF-ASSESSMENT to assess starting maturity

In order to determine the starting capacity and the foundation for developing the ERA Hub, the ecosystem stakeholders can benefit from employing the SELF-ASSESSMENT. The SELF-ASSESSMENT is an online resource designed to let ecosystems determine their maturity within each of the seven lines of action. Through a series of questions, the SELF-ASSESSMENT explores the institutions, resources and connections already present in the ecosystem and highlights the regional ecosystem's strengths and areas for improvement. The self-assessment questionnaire goes beyond facts or indicators available in public repositories, aiming to collect more in-depth information that often requires a qualitative assessment. For this reason, the self-assessment process will be an interactive, co-creative process, based on discussion between different actors in the ecosystem, each bringing

their own view on the situation and discussing the underlying reasons or patterns for each topic. By discussing the questions and trying to get to a consensual answer for each of them, the actors will be able to provide a more balanced answer to the question on the situation as is, but also come to a joint understanding of the strengths of the ecosystem and its gaps. For this reason, it is paramount that all stakeholders are represented in the assessment to gain a comprehensive and balanced view of the ecosystem.

The SELF-ASSESSMENT will provide a realistic view on the current maturity level of the ecosystem and will help to create a better understanding of the needs and possible actions to further strengthen it. The questionnaire returns an overall maturity score for the ecosystem as well as maturity scores for each line of action, ranging from 1 to 5 in accordance with the model shown in Figure 3:

Figure 3 Maturity scale showing the five levels of maturity from Absence to Collaboration. Adapted from Leveraging complexity for ecosystemic innovation, Russel & Smorodinskaya (2018)

- **Absence (level 1)** describes isolated efforts with little or no interaction and communication between players, few and scattered resources, and no governance frameworks in place.
- **Emergence (level 2)** entails early initiatives towards interaction and information sharing between ecosystem players, limited availability or awareness of resources, and inconsistent frameworks.
- **Development (level 3)** describes the alignment of activities between ecosystem players to achieve complementary goals, access to resources and talent, and early international orientation.
- **Diffusion (level 4)** relates to a coordinated effort across ecosystem players, structured and collaborative utilisation of resources, as well as international recognition and talent attraction.
- **Collaboration (level 5)** is the highest level of maturity and entails symbiotic and seamless integration between all quadruple helix players, joint sense of identity and well-defined shared goals, and international innovation leadership.

These benchmark scores are intended as a basis for discussion about the ecosystem’s strengths, ambitions and areas for improvement and a guide for selecting appropriate tools from the TOOLBOX.

The SELF-ASSESSMENT is available in the Material Hub of the COOPERATE website here: [COOPERATE Material Hub](#).

Identify suitable tools from the TOOLBOX

Based on the results of the SELF-ASSESSMENT, the core group will be able to select appropriate tools to implement in order to enhance the maturity of the regional R&I ecosystem. The TOOLBOX contains 33 specific tools, described in operational detail, representing best practices sourced from advanced knowledge and innovation ecosystems that are already closely aligned with the ERA Hub model. Each tool is described in terms of the value it brings to the ecosystem, the prerequisites that must be present to implement the tool, the potential challenges to implementing the tool and an implementation guide indicating how to execute the action. In addition, each tool is accompanied by references to real-life examples of how these tools have been successfully implemented, for inspiration.

The selection of tools should be based on a match between the regional ecosystem’s maturity levels and the recommended maturity levels for each tool and should align with the ecosystem’s strategic goals.

The tools pertaining to each line of action are shown in Table 1. The full tool descriptions are available in the COOPERATE Material Hub here: [COOPERATE Material Hub](#).

Tool	Research	Talent	Knowledge transfer	Funding	Collaboration	Governance	Innovation
Attractive living conditions		x					
Career fair		x	x				
Central interest organisation			x		x	x	
Centres of excellence	x			x			x
Commissioned research for industry	x		x	x			
Commissioned research/analysis for government	x		x	x			
Curricular and/or extracurricular courses in innovation and entrepreneurship		x					x
Diversity outreach		x					
Exchange programmes			x		x		x
Fairs and conferences	x		x				
Funding application support	x			x			
Grants and soft funding	x			x			x
Incentivising private investment	x			x			x

Industrial PhD	x	x	x				
Industry involvement in university courses		x	x		x		
Industry sponsorships	x			x			x
Industry-sponsored prizes	x	x		x			
Innovation hub				x	x		x
Investor society				x			x
Joint research initiatives	x	x	x				
Mentorship programme		x	x				x
MiniSprint		x	x				x
OpenInnovation		x	x				x
Popular science events		x	x				
Stakeholder engagement forum			x		x	x	
Stakeholder engagement platform			x	x		x	
Startup day/investor networking		x		x			x
Start-up programmes		x					x
Strategic partnerships	x		x		x		
Targeted funding programmes for young talent		x		x			
Technology transfer office			x		x		x
Thematic challenges		x			x		x
Trust-building activities					x	x	

Table 1 Overview of which tools pertain to which lines of action

Connect with other hubs through the PLATFORM

The PLATFORM is an online resource to support ecosystems in their transition to becoming an ERA Hub. The platform is available through the project website and contains four main elements: The present PLAYBOOK, the SELF-ASSESSMENT, the TOOLBOX, and a prototype of a mapping and matching tool.

The mapping and matching tool has two core functions and objectives:

Firstly, it provides information on ERA Hubs across Europe, giving context of their respective strengths and levels of maturity. This will allow ERA Hubs to evaluate how they compare to other hubs both in terms of the overall maturity score, and in terms of maturity within each of the seven lines of action.

The second purpose is to facilitate interaction between ERA Hubs to foster collaboration beyond regional and national borders on e.g. joint research projects, strategic partnerships, and international innovation discussions.

Specifically, the mapping and matching tool will detail contact points for each ERA Hub. This initiative is intended to facilitate connection and collaboration between hubs, inviting ecosystems to be inspired by each other and draw on each other's experiences.

This interconnected network strengthens individual ecosystems by fostering cross-border partnerships and creating synergies that accelerate technological advancements and societal impact.

Region: CZ01
Country: Czechia
University: Czech Technical University Prague
Main Contact: Ondrej Durkac - ondrej.durkac@cvut.cz

Organisations in the Hub

- Universities:
- [Czech Technical University Prague](#)
 - [Charles University](#)
 - [Masaryk University](#)
 - [University of Life Science Prague](#)
 - [Prague University of Economics and Business](#)
 - [University of Chemistry and Technology Prague](#)
 - [Palacký University Olomouc](#)
 - [University of Technology Brno](#)

- Research and Technology organisations:
- [Czech Invest](#)

Scope:
 The Czech innovation ecosystem is characterised by strong expertise in Engineering, ICT, Advanced Manufacturing and Materials Science. Key fields include Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, Cybersecurity, Nanotechnology and Biotechnology. Application areas focus on Industry 4.0, Automotive & Mobility, Energy & Clean Technologies, Healthcare Innovation and Aerospace.

Short description:
 Czech regions focus on advancing Digital Technologies, Smart Manufacturing and Sustainable Innovation

Maturity Score: 2.4

Figure 4 Example of the mapping and matching tool on the PLATFORM

Conclusion and future development

The PLAYBOOK is a guide for ecosystems aiming to improve their maturity and improve knowledge valorisation in the ecosystem. Structured around seven key lines of action—Research, Talent, Knowledge Transfer, Funding, Collaboration, Governance, and Innovation—it provides a robust framework that encompasses vital aspects of ecosystem development. It is the intention that these insights prompt self-evaluation of current strategies and the adoption of new mechanisms to improve knowledge valorisation to the benefit of all. It is the result of a collaborative and inclusive effort across the consortium partners with input from key members of regional R&I ecosystems in Europe.

For the PLAYBOOK to continue to evolve, it, along with the TOOLBOX and SELF-ASSESSMENT, would ideally be continually refined and expanded based on the experiences of real ecosystems using the tools to improve knowledge valorisation. As part of the COOPERATE project, the PLAYBOOK and the other tools will be tested in the regions of Lodz (Poland) and Centre-Val-de-Loire (France). The future implementation of the ERA Hub model will require a continuous update of the PLAYBOOK to maintain its relevance, effectiveness and applicability within the evolving European and global research and innovation landscape.

Bibliography

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